

LINGUOCULTURAL INTERFERENCE AND POSSIBILITIES TO OVERCOME IT (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH INTO RUSSIAN)

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the actual problem of overcoming linguocultural interference in the process of a foreign language learning. The research aim is to study the possibilities of overcoming linguocultural interference by native Russian speakers when learning English. Having used various methods of analyses the article's author comes to the conclusion that overcoming linguocultural interference is possible by referring different types dictionaries, linguoculturological mini-texts, as well as explaining the use in English metaphors and performing exercises to compare the use of lexical units in context in English and Russian. The author considers the development of a special set of exercises to overcome linguocultural interference in the process of English learning as a promising research area.*

Keywords: *linguistic and cultural interference, principles and stages of overcoming, English, native Russian speakers, linguistic and cultural worldview, interlingual communication.*

Introduction. The problem of linguocultural interference is studied by many scientists [2; 15]. A person perceives reality through the prism of his linguistic and cultural pictures of the world. The picture of the world is a complex of systematized holistic ideas, opinions and knowledge of human communities and an individual (thinking subject) based on worldview, worldview, worldview and worldview about the world and the universe, as well as about creative and cognitive abilities, the meaning of life and the place of a person in the world. [1, p. 231; 4, p. 118]. In each picture of the world, ideas (ordinary, religious, scientific, philosophical and aesthetic consciousness) that correspond to the meaning of life and value ideas of an individual predominate. The German philosopher Karl Jaspers considered the totality of subject content that a person possesses as a picture of the world [10, p. 62]. The term "picture of the world" itself appeared in science thanks to the works of the German physicist G. Hertz. He described the variety of objects of the outside world that developed in the process of studying objects of the outside world by different researchers. Hertz's conclusions were developed by M. Planck, who developed the definition of the physical picture of the world. In his opinion, this is a "sample of the world", which is being formed in physical science and is a reflection of natural laws. After these scientists described the physical picture of the world, definitions of the biological, chemical, demographic, economic, pedagogical, aesthetic, technical, cultural, linguistic and other pictures of the world began to appear in accordance with the field of knowledge in which the authors of these concepts worked [6, p. 45].

In the context of our research, linguistic and cultural pictures of the world are of particular interest. In this regard, let us dwell in more detail on these concepts and the features of their study in various scientific works. In its content, the cultural picture of the world is a complex of rational knowledge and ideas about the norms, values, customs, mentality of one's own culture and the cultures of other peoples. It includes unconscious meanings, personal meanings, assessments and experiences [6, p. 48].

The linguistic picture of the world is one of the most interesting and meaningful topics in linguistics. However, up to the present time, science has not yet formed a sufficiently clear idea of

the meaning that this concept is filled with. At the same time, the problem of the relationship between culture, language and consciousness is considered from different angles: many studies have been conducted on the linguistic picture of the world among speakers of a particular language, associative dictionaries of various languages have been developed, containing rich material that allows one to deeply study the features of perception of reality by representatives of one culture [11, p. 116].

Of course, the languages of culture are very diverse, because by their nature, according to M.S. Kagan, "culture is multilingual". All languages of culture have their own distinctive features and cannot be adequately translated into other languages of the world. The term "linguistic picture of the world" is based on the ideas of Wilhelm von Humboldt and the neo-Humboldtians on the inner form of language, as well as on the ideas of American ethnolinguistics, especially the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis of linguistic relativity. It was the linguist Humboldt who first drew attention to the national content of language and thinking, pointing out that different languages become for nations the organs of their original perception and thinking. Any person sees a subjective image of a certain object, which does not completely coincide with the image of the same object in other people. This, in fact, unique representation can be objectified only by making its way through the mouth into the outside world. In this regard, words include a complex of subjective ideas that differ only within specific limits, since their speakers are members of the same language community, have a specific national consciousness and character [3, p. 26].

The term "linguistic picture of the world" entered science thanks to the works of Leo Weisgerber. This concept gave originality to his linguo-philosophical theory, together with such categories as "intermediate world" and "language energy". The linguistic picture of the world is a system of all potential contents: spiritual, which provide the originality of the mentality and culture of a particular linguistic community, and linguistic, which support the existence and functioning of the language itself. The linguistic picture of the world forms the homogeneity of the linguistic essence, helping to consolidate linguistic and cultural originality in the perception of the world and express it by linguistic means. National experience forms specific features at all levels of the language. The specificity of the language that exists in the minds of a particular community (people, native speakers) creates a certain linguistic picture of the world through which a person perceives the world around [7, p. 34].

Language is a fact of culture, its integral part, which is inherited and at the same time appears as an instrument of culture. The linguistic picture of the world as a common cultural heritage of the nation has a complex structure and many levels. It provides the specifics of the communicative behavior not only of individual individuals – carriers of a particular culture and language, but also the features of the speech interaction of a particular society.

A representative of a certain linguocultural community perceives and evaluates all objects and phenomena of the surrounding world not only in spatial and temporal categories, but also in their meanings, which include numerous intrasystemic connections. Intercultural interaction leads to the mutual influence of language pictures of representatives of different linguocultural communities, so their interference becomes linguocultural. The meanings of vocabulary acquire a certain cultural stereotype, which becomes one of the options for the image of a fragment of the world of representatives of another people.

The meaning of a lexical unit and the context have a two-way relationship, when, on the one hand, its meaning depends on the context (the usual scenario for the development of the situation), and, on the other hand, the lexical unit itself produces a predictable, desirable scenario

(context). According to P. Violi, the conceptual action corresponds to the empirical characterization of semantic representations. In other words, lexical units are understood when they are projected onto the complex life experience of a representative of a particular linguocultural community. This means that the semantics of the language directly depends on the “semantics” of life and the experience accumulated by many generations [16, p. 43].

V.V. Krasny in his study comes to the conclusion that a complex of knowledge and ideas about extralinguistic phenomena (customs, traditions, way of life, norms and rules of behavior in a particular linguocultural community, a national picture of the world based on a special perception of the surrounding world, mentality, artistic culture of the people) is formed cognitive structures and, like linguistic knowledge, is a significant part of the communicative competence of a particular person [13, p. 64]. Of course, when this complex is verbalized, there is a risk of linguocultural interference, due to the different communicative and cultural significance of a particular phenomenon for representatives of different linguocultural communities in terms of communication. In the theory of interlingual communication, linguocultural interference is the transfer to the elements of the language being studied of part of the linguistic and paralinguistic properties of the native language, which directly depend on the facts of the native linguoculture [9, p. 45]. These facts can be manifested in the cultural connotation of language units, current national stereotypes, images, symbols and standards.

V.N. Telia was engaged in the study of cultural connotation, considering it a method of manifestation of culture in linguistic signs. The scientist came to the conclusion that the national and cultural features of a language unit constitute a “link” that unites the “sign body” with symbols, images, standards, concepts and stereotypes of national culture, which are mastered by the people as a native speaker [12, p. 126].

Materials and methods. When writing a scientific article, the following research methods were applied: analysis of scientific literature, linguocultural analysis, comparative analysis, complex analysis, induction, deduction, generalization and prediction of minimizing linguocultural interference of different types when using certain principles and stages of working with English lexical units. The study materials were explanatory and word-formation English-Russian dictionaries.

Results. Linguistic literature distinguishes different types of linguocultural interference: phonetic, semantic, lexical; grammatical, stylistic, sociocultural and others. Within the framework of this article, we do not aim to consider all these types, so we will analyze those that are most common and present ways to overcome them. In particular, phonetic interference is widely known, when in words in English, for example, “industry” (in Russ. «промышленность»), “botany” (in Russ. «ботаника»), “influence” (in Russ. «влияние»), “development” (in Russ. «развитие»), etc. the stress shifts under the influence of the native language.

N.P. Fedorova points out that in English there is a short and long vowel, which has a semantic function and leads to a communicative failure: for example, the incorrect replacement of a long vowel with a short one ([i:] vs. [i] - “seek” («искать») – “sick” («больной»), ([a:] vs. [ʌ] “dark” («темный») – “duck” («утка») or ignoring the semantically significant distinction between dentolabial and labial ([v] vs. [w]), sibilant and interdental ([s] vs. [θ/ð]) [12, c. 9].

In translation theory, there is the concept of “translator’s false friends”, which means the selection of a pair of lexical units in two languages that have similar spelling, origin and / or pronunciation, but different semantic meaning. Here are examples of “false friends of the translator” with incorrect and correct translation: “actual” (incorrect «актуальный», correct

«фактический»), “accurate” (incorrect «аккуратный», correct «точный»), “complexion” (incorrect «комплексия», correct «цвет лица»), “focus” (incorrect «фокус», correct «внимание»), “criminal” (incorrect «криминал», correct «преступник»), “original” (incorrect «оригинальный», correct «первоначальный»), “technique” (incorrect «техника», correct «метод»), “figure” (incorrect «фигура», correct «рисунок»), “major” (incorrect «майор», correct «мэр»), etc. Of course, there are many international words, for example, “globalization” («глобализация»), “communication” («коммуникация»), “information” («информация»), “management” («менеджмент»), “test” («тест»), which are translated by the method of tracing (literal translation), however, when studying English, in order to overcome semantic interference, one should carefully analyze the problems of “translator’s false friends”, identify such words and memorize their correct translation by referring to the dictionary.

Another type of linguocultural interference is grammatical interference. In particular, Russian prepositions have a destructive effect on the use of English prepositions; the meaning of the Russian preposition "in" in English is represented by various thematic prepositions of time, space and movement (at, on, in; to, in; into, etc.). A serious problem for learners of English is also the correct use of articles of definite (the) and indefinite (a, an) articles, since this grammatical category is completely absent in Russian. Russian native speakers often miss English articles in speech or use them incorrectly.

This type of linguocultural interference is widespread among native speakers of the Russian language, such as non-observance of the direct word order in English sentences. They forget that in an affirmative English sentence, the predicate must be preceded by the subject. This is due to the fact that the Russian language has a free word order in a sentence, for example, «я играл с друзьями», «с друзьями играл я», «я с друзьями играл», English, on the other hand, has a strictly fixed word order in a sentence: “I walked with my friends yesterday” – the subject is always before the predicate, and in impersonal sentences you cannot use only a noun, verb or adjective, as in Russian: «Солнечно», «Тепло», «Зима». The presence of an impersonal subject and predicate is obligatory. – “It’s sunny”, “It’s warm”, “It’s winter”, etc. The fixed word order in English gave rise to the Sapir-Whorf theory of linguistic relativity.

Even in the simplest phrases like “I am a student” («я студент») and “I am 18 years old” («мне 18 лет») mistakes are made, since the Russian language almost always lacks a linking verb to be «быть», for example, «я студент», «мне 18 лет», «я из Москвы». English sentences always have the linking verb “to be”.

Many difficulties with linguocultural interference arise when studying the tenses of an English verb. Due to the fact that there are only three tenses in Russian (present, past and future), it is difficult for a native speaker of this language to understand why Present Perfect Tense refers to the present line and not the past tense, while in Russian sentences: «Я уже купил», «я еще не купил» - indicate past tense. It is not easy to understand the fact that the Past Perfect Tense characterizes the so-called “past” time. We believe that it is most effective to perceive the situation through the category of “result” (if something matters now, we are talking about the present tense of the action performed, if it was important in the past, then it means the past tense).

The implementation of the methodology for overcoming linguocultural interference requires the development of principles that are adequate for the successful implementation of this process in the theory and practice of learning English. The most important principles include the following:

- The principle of relying on the native language;

- The principle of communicative orientation of training;
- The principle of good faith;
- The principle of clarity;
- The principle of consistency in the presentation of grammatical material;
- The principle of complication of mastering the types of speech activity;
- The principle of the gradual formation of grammatical skills and the development of speech skills;
- The principle of the adequacy of the use of grammatical means;
- The principle of taking into account grammatical difficulties in the process of interaction between languages [9, p. 72].

Sociocultural interference is generated by the very culture that a given language displays. This is due to differences in mentalities, value systems, ethical standards, etc. Interference appears when at least one of the participants in communication perceives similar realities, phenomena, norms of behavior in another culture through the prism of learned models of worldview, for example, English language learners often answer "please" («пожалуйста») in response to the phrase "thank you" («спасибо») or begin to talk about life's problems in response to the question "How are you?" («Как дела?»), despite the fact that in English linguistic culture it is customary to answer in a standard way "I'm fine, thank you" («Все отлично, спасибо»), or they say "good" («хорошо») in response to the question "How do you do?" («Как дела?»), although in reality, English speakers express a common greeting to a stranger in such a way that suggests the same counter-question "How do you do?" («Как дела?») or answer "Nice to meet you" («Рад нашей встрече»).

Reducing the level of linguocultural interference in the study of English seems to us, of course, a difficult task, however, it seems that the use of authentic educational materials, audio courses, newspapers, magazines, Internet materials, as well as the correct organization of work on the features of the English language lead to an increase in the level of English proficiency. language and, accordingly, in most cases minimizes linguistic and cultural interference of all kinds.

Discussion. Most scientists [13, p. 98; 14, p. 413] agrees that overcoming linguocultural interference should be dealt with already at the initial stages of learning English. Based on the analysis carried out in this article, we believe that it is useful to start a comprehensive analysis of the use of certain lexical units in English with an explanatory dictionary. The language dictates to the carrier "its own" worldview, which, as a result of this circumstance, is partially determined by the linguistic picture of the world. Due to the fact that representatives of different linguocultural communities see the world through the prism of their native language, they consider "their own" sign to be important in the named object (or phenomenon). This means that when studying the English language (as well as any other foreign language), in the process of mastering its linguocultural information, it is necessary to learn to "feel" the inner form of the word – to understand the motivation of the meaning of a particular lexical unit of the English language by the meaning of the morphemes included in its structure or the primary, initial meaning of the same word, to be aware of the idea underlying the nomination, its influence on the way of constructing the concept expressed in the word. The next stage of the complex analysis of the word may be an appeal to the explanatory word-formation dictionary. Further, work with a nationally marked lexical unit to determine its cumulative function should be continued within the framework of linguocultural mini-texts containing this lexical unit with different circumstances of use and variability of contextual meanings, if any. The final stage in the analysis of the cumulative function

of a particular lexeme can be an explanation of the use of metaphors containing this lexeme in English, as well as performing exercises to compare the use of this lexical unit in English and Russian.

Conclusion. At the end of our study, we emphasize that the prevention of linguocultural interference implies contextual work with a large amount of cultural material, which allows English speakers of the Russian language to better and easier understand the meanings of different linguocultures, contributes to the formation of skills associated with the use of such lexical units in speech, helps to expand the selection of lexical and grammatical means suitable for adequate transmission of information. Working with semantization and actualization of nationally marked vocabulary in speech to exclude linguocultural interference should not be reduced to recognizing its meanings. It is important to learn to “translate” such information from the directly linguistic sphere into the area of one's own picture of the world, which must be constantly expanded and enriched through deeper immersion in the language and its culture being studied.

REFERENCES

1. Айдукевич К. Картина мира и понятийный аппарат // Философия науки. Вып. 2: Гносеологические и логико-методологические проблемы. – М.: ИФ РАН, 2017. – 376 с.
2. Гальченко Р.Г. Методика преодоления интерференции в условиях многоязычия. – М.: Наука, 2012. – 312 с.
3. Гумбольд В. Фон. Язык и философия культуры. – М.: Прогресс. 1985. – 418 с.
4. Зорин В.И. Евразийская мудрость от А до Я: философский толковый словарь. – Алматы: Создік-Словарь, 2019. – С. 114-127.
5. Красных В.В. «Свой среди чужих»: миф или реальность? – М.: Гнозис, 2003. – 312 с.
6. Кузнецова Т. Ф. Культурная картина мира как ядро тезауруса в концепции Владимира Андреевича Лукова // Знание. Понимание. Умение. – М.: МосГУ, 2015. – № 3. – С. 41-52.
7. Постовалова В.И. Картина мира в жизнедеятельности человека // Роль человеческого фактора в языке: Язык и картина мира / отв. ред Б.А. Серебренников. – М.: Наука, 2020. – С. 30-43.
8. Телия В.Н. Русская фразеология. Семантический, прагматический и лингвокультурологический аспекты. – М.: школа «языки русской культуры», 1996. – 380 с.
9. Тимачев П.В. Лингвокультурная интерференция как коммуникативная помеха (на материале английского языка): дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Волгоград, 2018. – 174 с.
10. Удовиченко Е.М. Философия: конспект лекций и словарь терминов (элементарный курс): Учебное пособие. – Магнитогорск: МГТУ, 2019. – 265 с.
11. Федоров А.А. Введение в теорию и историю культуры: словарь. 2-е изд., стер. – М.: Флинта, 2012. – 387 с.
12. Федорова Н.П. Преодоление лингвокультурной интерференции в процессе обучения иностранному языку студентов неязыковых вузов (на материале английского языка). Автореф. дисс... канд. пед. наук / Н.П. Федорова. – Нижний Новгород, 2010. – 42 с.
13. Diebold, A. Incipient bilingualism // Language. – 2020. – No 1. – 96-105 pp.
14. Hockett, Ch. A Course in Modern Linguistics. No. 4. – N.Y.: Print, 1997. – 410-419 pp.
15. Kharkhurin, A.V. The Role of Cross-linguistic and Cross-cultural experience in Bilinguals Divergent Thinking // Cognitive Aspects of Bilingualism, 2007. – 175–210 pp.

16. Violi, P. Meaning and Experience. Blooming and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, 2001. – 156 p.